

Supplemental Table 1. Regression analyses of the association between storage and transport time (in hours) of EDTA samples and each of the biomarkers.

Biomarkers are on the log scale; time in hours

Biomarker	<i>n</i>	Coefficient	95% CI		<i>p</i>
IL-10	427	0.006	-0.015	0.028	0.554
TNF- α	427	-0.010	-0.020	0.000	0.059
sTNF-RII	393	0.002	-0.008	0.013	0.652
sFlt-1	394	0.027	0.012	0.042	0.001
Apo-B	427	0.002	-0.008	0.013	0.639
Leptin	427	-0.014	-0.031	0.003	0.097

Supplemental Table 2. Regression analyses of the association between chorioamnionitis infection and each of the biomarkers at delivery.

Biomarkers are on the log scale; Coeff = coefficient; 2 of women with chorioamnionitis did not have biomarker samples at delivery

Biomarker	<i>n</i>	Coeff.	95% CI		<i>p</i>
IL-10	64	0.30	-0.15	0.75	0.177
TNF- α	64	0.20	-0.07	0.47	0.148
sTNF-RII	58	-0.17	-0.36	0.02	0.083
sFlt-1	55	-0.21	-0.59	0.18	0.277
Apo-B	64	0.02	-0.22	0.27	0.851
Leptin	64	0.13	-0.43	0.70	0.629

Supplemental Table 3. Association of biomarker levels with low birth weight by regression analyses with robust variance estimators

Biomarkers are on the log scale, twins and stillborn babies excluded. OR = odds ratio; All TNF- α values in women who were malaria positive and gave birth to a low birth weight baby were undetectable.

Biomarker	<i>N</i>	OR	95% CI		<i>p</i>
<i>Delivery</i>					
IL-10	149	0.96	0.64	1.44	0.849
TNF- α	149	0.45	0.11	1.93	0.283
sTNF-RII	137	0.70	0.25	1.93	0.490
sFlt-1	127	1.15	0.39	3.34	0.800
Apo-B	149	0.50	0.15	1.66	0.257
Leptin	149	1.48	0.77	2.87	0.240
<i>Third trimester</i>					
IL-10	141	1.20	0.56	2.59	0.638
TNF- α	141	0.67	0.13	3.52	0.632
sTNF-RII	137	0.51	0.06	4.24	0.530
sFlt-1	134	1.32	0.45	3.91	0.615
Apo-B	141	0.67	0.25	1.80	0.429
Leptin	141	1.80	0.67	4.81	0.241
<i>Second trimester</i>					
IL-10	123	1.24	0.54	2.84	0.607
TNF- α	-	-	-	-	-
sTNF-RII	105	1.00	0.27	3.70	0.999
sFlt-1	119	0.38	0.06	2.21	0.280
Apo-B	123	0.81	0.25	2.56	0.715
Leptin	123	0.82	0.49	1.38	0.459